

CHARACTERISTICS OF DISTANCE EDUCATION

Bukhara State University

foundation doctoral student

Sidikova Dilora Shavkatovna

Abstract: this article provides information about the characteristic features of distance education. At the same time, the advantages and disadvantages of distance education are highlighted.

Key words: distance education, traditional education, training courses, innovative methods, independent study, creative activity, form of education.

Distance education is currently one of the most modern, popular and popular types of education, which does not require participants to have a fixed place, schedule and other commitments. Distance education is a form of education based on information and telecommunication technologies, including part-time and full-time education, including the best traditional and innovative methods, teaching tools and forms. Distance learning is an educational system based on new information technologies, telecommunication technologies and technical means.

Distance education differs from traditional education in the following characteristics:

Flexibility - the possibility for the learner to receive education at a convenient time, place and speed;

Modularity - the possibility of creating a training plan suitable for individual or group needs from a set of independent training courses - modules;

Parallelism - the possibility of carrying out educational activities in parallel with work activities, that is, without separating them from production;

Comprehensiveness is the ability of a large number of students to simultaneously access large educational resources (electronic library, information and knowledge base, etc.). This is an opportunity for a large number of students to communicate with each other and with the teacher using communication tools.

Economic efficiency - effective use of training areas, equipment, vehicles, and training materials, gathering training materials together, making them look organized and providing a large number of references to this information reduces the costs of training specialists.

Social equality is the opportunity to receive equal education for everyone, regardless of the student's place of residence, health, and level of financial support.

Internationality is the ability to import and export achievements that meet world standards in the field of education. The new role of the teacher - distance education further expands and updates the role of the teacher in the teaching process. Now the teacher is mastering the process it is required to coordinate, regularly improve the subject they teach in accordance with news and innovations, deepen their level and creative activity.

Quality - the distance education method is not inferior to full-time education in terms of quality of education. Perhaps, by attracting local and foreign teaching staff, it can increase the quality of the organization of the educational process by using the best teaching-methodical textbooks and control tests.

Distance learning is independent learning. Independent reading develops a person's ability to think independently, assess the situation, conclude and predict. Another advantage of distance learning is that the student can study at his own convenience and even without leaving work. It is because of these advantages that this method is widely used in the world today. Another advantage of distance education is that the student himself determines the duration of the study, that is, the student starts studying at the time of his/her choice, learns the materials under the supervision of the teacher. Mastering is determined by completing assignments and tests. The faster the student learns the given program, the faster he graduates and receives a certificate. If he cannot master the program, he will be given the opportunity to work independently and continue his studies.

Advantages and disadvantages of distance education:

In fact, the majority of applicants who choose distance learning are those who do not want to give up their work, but want to learn. With online education, you can study on the weekends, or even in the middle of the night when you get home from work;

Your money will be saved. For any program, the distance learning rate can be much cheaper than the regular tuition at the training centers. For students looking for affordable options, online education is the best option;

Save your time! You can save time spent waiting for transport to and from study centers. In online education, you get information in the area you want;

If a student is ambitious, the biggest benefit of distance learning is that some classes are taught in groups. In the group, some students understand faster, and some more slowly. In this respect, distance education method is more effective;

Disadvantages:

The possibility of confusion is high. There are no face-to-face teachers and no classmates to constantly remind you about upcoming assignments. If a student wants to successfully complete a distance learning course, he or she needs to be motivated and focused;

Disconnect from the network. The biggest enemy of learning online is a slow internet service provider or disconnection. In this situation, the student's desire to learn fades or becomes nervous.

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